

Biostimulation of sulfate reduction for in-situ metal(loid) precipitation at an industrial site in Flanders, Belgium

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Native sulfate reducing bacteria were biostimulated in the presence of high sulfate levels
- Change from iron-oxidizing to strictly anoxic conditions by the addition of organic substrate triggered sulfate reduction
- In-situ metal(loid)s removal by (co)precipitation as biogenic mineral sulfides was confirmed by stable isotope analysis and mineralogy
- Microbial amplicon sequencing and shotgun metagenomics revealed the genus *Desulfosporosinus* as the major sulfate reducer

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

A 30-month pilot study was conducted to evaluate the potential of in-situ metal(loid) removal through biostimulation of sulfate-reducing processes. The study took place at an industrial site in Flanders, Belgium, known for metal(loid) contamination in soil and groundwater. Biostimulation involved two incorporations of an organic substrate (emulsified vegetable oil) as electron donor and potassium bicarbonate to raise the pH of the groundwater by 1–1.5 units. The study focused on the most impacted permeable fine sand aquifer (8–9 m below groundwater level) confined by layers of non-permeable clay. The fine sands exhibited initially oxic conditions (50–200 mV), an acidic pH of 4.5 and sulfate concentrations ranging from 600 to 800 mg/L. At the central monitoring well, anoxic conditions (–200 to –400 mV) and a pH of 5.9 established shortly after the second substrate and reagent injection. Over the course of 12 months, there was a significant decrease in the concentration of arsenic (from 2500 to 12 µg/L), nickel (from 360 to <2 µg/L), zinc (from 78,000 to <2 µg/L), and

Abbreviations: CSIA, Compound specific isotope analysis; DOC, Dissolved organic carbon; DSR, Dissimilatory sulfate reduction; EDX, Energy dispersive X-ray; EOS, Emulsified oil suspension; ISMP, In-situ metal(loid) precipitation; ROI, Radius of influence; SEM, Scanning Electron Microscopy; SRB, Sulfate reducing bacteria; XRD, X-ray diffraction; XRF, X-ray fluorescence.

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sulfate (from 930 to 450 mg/L). Low levels of metal(loid)s were still present after 34 months (end of study). Mineralogical analysis indicated that the precipitates formed were amorphous in nature. Evidence for biologically driven metal(loid) precipitation was provided by compound specific stable isotope analysis of sulfate. In addition, changes in microbial populations were assessed using next-generation sequencing, revealing stimulation of native sulfate-reducing bacteria. These results highlight the potential of biostimulation for long-term in situ metal(loid) plume treatment/containment.

1. Introduction

Groundwater at sites with a history of mining and metallurgical activities is often acidic and contains high concentrations of sulfate, dissolved metals and metalloids. These contaminants can easily spread beyond the site boundaries, impacting surface water bodies, drinking water reservoirs, and agricultural wells (Han et al., 2023). Due to their high toxicity, persistence and bioaccumulative nature, the presence of elevated levels of metals and metalloids in water resources poses a significant risk to human health, as well as the overall health and biodiversity of connected water bodies (Ravindra and Mor, 2019; Ahmad et al., 2021).

The distribution of metal(loid)s in groundwater depends on multiple factors including the physico-chemical properties of the groundwater (e.g., pH, redox potential, quantity and quality of organic matter, presence of other elements), the geology of the aquifer (matrix granulometry and mineral composition), the inherent physico-chemical properties of the metal(loid)s and the hydrogeology of the subsurface (e.g., aquifer permeability and thickness, groundwater flow and velocity) (Evanko and Dzombak, 1997; USEPA, 2007b; Hölting and Coldewey, 2013). These factors significantly influence the main mechanisms governing the fate of metal(loid)s in the subsurface including adsorption/desorption on mineral surfaces (e.g. clay minerals, Fe and Mn oxides and oxyhydroxides), complexation to organic matter and precipitation (as hydroxides, carbonates, phosphates and sulfides) (Adriano, 2001). In addition, biological processes can significantly impact the environmental fate of metal(loid)s in the subsurface by various mechanisms including bioaccumulation inside the cell, biosorption on the cell membrane, direct biotransformation via redox reactions, indirect biomineralization/precipitation or biodegradation of metal(loid) chelating agents (Tabak et al., 2005; Hashim et al., 2011; Pérez-de-Mora et al., 2014a; Su et al., 2022).

Depositional environments such as alluvial deposits are common hydrogeologic settings characterized by alternating layers of fine and less fine or coarser grained materials that result in contrasting hydraulic conductivities of >2 or 3 orders of magnitude (Puigserver et al., 2013, 2020; Şen, 2015). According to Freeze and Cherry (1979) the term aquifer describes highly permeable geologic units that can transmit significant amounts of water under moderate hydraulic gradients. In contrast, aquitards are less permeable strata that can still transmit water in quantities enough to influence the regional groundwater, but are not permeable enough to allow the completion of exploitation wells. As the term aquiclude to describe an impermeable unit has become obsolete, the term aquitard is usually coined to describe the less permeable layers (Ge and Gorelick, 2015). Thus, in an interbedded sand-silt sequence, the silts may be considered aquitards, whereas in a silt-clay system, they are aquifers. At impacted sites, the distribution of contaminants in stratigraphic sequences can be highly heterogeneous. For instance, discontinuities in the less permeable layer can result in contamination of several interbedded permeable layers. In addition, both organic and inorganic contaminants can accumulate in layers of fine materials that act, in turn, as secondary contaminant sources, resulting in a prolonged contaminant delivery, particularly for organic contaminants (Puigserver et al., 2016). In the more permeable layers a contamination plume generally forms, the length of which depends largely on the physico-chemical properties of the contaminant (e.g. solubility in water) the natural attenuation capacity of the aquifer matrix and its hydraulic conductivity, with more

permeable layers generally resulting in larger plumes. While less conductive but permeable layers (e.g., fine sands and silts) may result in smaller plumes for the same contaminant, they may exhibit greater persistence once the contaminant source is removed or remediated. In addition, fine-textured layers can be difficult to remediate by both ex-situ and in-situ approaches due to their limited hydraulic yield and poor substrate/reagent distribution (Marnette et al., 2022). Conventional ex-situ treatment of metal(loid)-contaminated groundwater typically involves pumping the groundwater to the surface and removing the metal(loid)s through methods such as chemical (co)precipitation (e.g., as metal hydroxides, sulfides, or coprecipitates with ferrite), ion exchange resins, or adsorption on zeolite filters (Pohl, 2020). The treated water can then be re-infiltrated, discharged into the rainwater system, or used for other purposes (US EPA, 2007a). However, ex-situ treatment applications can be expensive, time-consuming, generate additional waste, and are not always feasible. Therefore, in-situ applications can provide a viable treatment alternative for specific sites and contamination scenarios.

In-situ chemical precipitation of metal hydroxides/carbonates after increasing the pH is not practical due to the expected re-dissolution of metals when pH returns to its original acidic level, particularly in the case of metal hydroxides (Lewis, 2010). Precipitation as sulfide minerals is more advantageous due to the lower solubility of the sulfide precipitates, their non-amphoteric nature, and stability over a wide pH range (Malik et al., 2019). However, incorporation of sulfide sources for metal (co)precipitation may be costly and challenging due to the low solubility of the sulfide sources (e.g. FeS and CaS) and the rapid formation of hydrogen sulfide after application of soluble reagents such as sodium sulfide and sodium hydrosulfide (Pohl, 2020). In recent years, the application of nanomaterials for in-situ remediation of heavy metal (loid) contaminated sediments and groundwater has gained considerable interest (Cai et al., 2019). However, homogenous nanoparticle distribution in the subsurface is usually very limited, especially in less permeable aquifers. An alternative solution for contaminated groundwater with sulfate in excess of metal(loid)s is biological in-situ precipitation as stable sulfide minerals, which can be achieved by stimulating native sulfate-reducing bacteria (SRB).

SRB are versatile microorganisms that can use sulfate as an electron acceptor via dissimilatory sulfate reduction (DSR) pathway. SRB are able to grow both heterotrophically, using organic molecules, and autotrophically, using H_2 as the electron donor and CO_2 as the carbon source. In the presence of sulfate and under anoxic conditions, SRB can be biostimulated to reduce sulfate and precipitate metal(loid)s in-situ as sulfide minerals (Saunders et al., 2005; Keimowitz et al., 2007; Kirk et al., 2010; Omoregie et al., 2013; Sun et al., 2016; Hu et al., 2020). Biostimulation can be achieved by incorporating an excess of a fermentable organic substrate (e.g., lactate, molasses, emulsified vegetable oil) that can be transformed by native communities into small organic acids and hydrogen. These, in turn, may serve as a carbon source and electron donor for the reduction of sulfate to sulfide via DSR, followed by chemical precipitation of sulfide with metal contaminants. Although microbial studies on the biostimulation of SRB for heavy metal remediation in natural environments are scarce, bioreactors are routinely used to study enriched microbial communities for this purpose. Such microbial communities are usually dominated by the genus *Desulfovibrio*, although other taxa such as *Desulfomicrobium* and *Desulfosporosinus* can also be prevalent depending on operational conditions

and source of inoculum (Kiran et al., 2017; Qian et al., 2019). Recently, the identification of DSR genes in environmental metagenomes have revealed a large diversity of bacteria capable of DSR, including a number of uncultured species, revealing their ubiquitous distribution in nature (Diao et al., 2023).

The DSR process is sensitive to environmental parameters, such as redox potential, dissolved oxygen, and pH. Anaerobic environments and reducing conditions favor microbial sulfate reduction, whereas higher redox potentials can inhibit this process (Bernardez et al., 2013). In addition, although SRB are ubiquitous; different taxa have adapted to acidic, neutral or alkaline conditions (Barton and Fauque, 2022). In the field, SRB have been observed in acidic environments with high metal concentrations, such as acidic salt ponds (Sánchez-España et al., 2020) and acid mine drainage (Sanchez-Andrea et al., 2012). Acidophilic SRB, although capable of sulfate reduction at pH as low as 3.6, exhibit optimal sulfate reduction at pH above 5 (Barton and Fauque, 2022). In addition, anoxic aquifers with low pH promote iron reduction relative to sulfate reduction (Kirk et al., 2016), therefore pH correction coupled to biostimulation may be necessary to drive efficient sulfate reduction in acidic aquifers with significant iron concentrations.

While the potential of biostimulation to drive precipitation of sulfide metal(loid)s has long been known, and applications for ex-situ treatment of acid mine tailings in bioreactors have gained interest in recent years (Zhang and Wang, 2014; Kefeni et al., 2017; Li et al., 2023), in-situ field applications for groundwater treatment are very limited (Lookman et al., 2013; Pi et al., 2017) despite demonstrated potential in laboratory studies (Satyawali et al., 2011; Saunders et al., 2018; Li et al., 2023). The main reason for this remains the concern about the stability of the metal (loid) precipitates when aquifer conditions change, particularly groundwater pH and/or redox potential, or when the organic substrate supplied as electron donor is depleted. Janssen and Temminghoff (2004) reported that biological sulfate reduction continued for at least 2 months after cessation of substrate addition, while an immediate increase in Zn concentrations in the system was observed. Satyawali et al. (2010) investigated the stability of Zn and Co precipitates formed after in-situ metal(loid) precipitation in batch reactors consisting of a natural aquifer solids and metal-contaminated groundwater. The authors reported that the Zn precipitate was not affected by redox changes, but up to 58 % of the Zn was mobilized from the solid matrix following sequential pH changes. Unfortunately, there is a significant lack of long-term field studies investigating the feasibility of in-situ metal(loid) precipitation for aquifer treatment and the dynamics of the SRB and subsurface microbial communities. A better understanding of biogeochemical processes in real environments is crucial to assess the potential and sustainability of this approach.

In this study, we investigate the potential of biostimulating native SRB for in-situ metal(loid) precipitation at a challenging industrial setting with a long history of metal(loid) (As, Ni and Zn) contamination, acidic and oxic groundwater conditions, low permeability and elevated concentrations of sulfate and iron driven by anthropogenic activities. To better understand the biogeochemical interactions responsible for successful or limited biological sulfate reduction at specific wells and stages of the active treatment process, we employed a combined approach. Our study involved monitoring groundwater for up to 34 months at different locations (one central monitoring well and two peripheral wells) and conducting the following investigations: i) analysis of general groundwater field parameters such as pH, electrical conductivity, dissolved oxygen, and temperature, ii) analysis of metal(loid)s, bicarbonate, sulfate, sulfide, dissolved organic carbon, Fe(II), and Fe(III) concentrations, iii) mineralogical analysis of precipitates by SEM-EDX (scanning electron microscopy-energy dispersive x-ray), XRD (x-ray diffraction) and XRF (x-ray fluorescence), iv) compound-specific isotope analysis of sulfate, and iv) qualitative analysis of microbial community composition and functional potential using next-generation amplicon and shotgun sequencing.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The field pilot study took place at an active industrial site in northern Flanders with a large history of metallurgical activity since the 19th century, which is part of two EU research and innovation actions aimed at reaching zero pollution in Europe (GREENER Grant 826,312 and BIOSYSMO Grant 101,060,211). The Site geology consists of a succession of various alternating layers of quaternary and tertiary sands, interspersed with important local clay layers. The clay layers act as aquitards/aquicludes that confine the more permeable fine sand layers through which groundwater flows. The hydrogeological sequence to a maximum depth of 13 m below ground level (mbgl) is featured by i) fine sands with a kf-value of $2\text{--}3 \times 10^{-5}$ m/s and located at depths between 0 and 3.5 m and 6.5 to 9.0 m, and ii) clays with a kf-value of $1\text{--}6 \times 10^{-7}$ m/s and located at depths between 3.5–6.5 m and 9.0–13.0 m. The horizontal groundwater flow in the fine sand layers is N to S/SW with a hydraulic gradient (i) of approx. 0.001 that results in groundwater velocity of approx. 6–9.5 m/y, assuming an effective porosity of 10 %. Between 1918 and 1942 different acts of war including the outbreak of a large fire in a former electrolysis hall resulted in the spillage of large amounts of acid electrolyte, sulfuric acid, and metal(loid)s into the subsurface. The contamination reached the second layer of fine sands indicating that this layer was not completely confined as initially thought according to the soil surveys. Over the years a metal(loid) contamination plume evolved from the original brine source area resulting in substantial downstream concentrations in the mg/L range for As, Fe, Ni, Zn, and sulfate, as well as low pH (3–5 units). Table S1 of the Supplementary Material provides an overview of the background and regulatory limits for soil and groundwater in Flanders. Representative soil and groundwater characteristics for the pilot study area are included in Tables S2–S4 of the Supplementary Material.

2.2. Treatability tests and field pilot design

In order to address the contamination problem, a remediation treatment assessment was performed. The assessment included remedial options both for the contamination source and the plume. Due to the low groundwater velocity and high levels of sulfate and iron content, a laboratory treatability study using site materials and including incubations in batch reactors and a column study were conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of SRB to precipitate metal(loid)s in-situ. The characteristics of the soil and groundwater samples for the treatability tests are provided in Tables S2–S4 of the Supplementary Material. A full description of the batch and column treatability studies is provided in Text S1 and S2 in the Supplementary Material. In the batch study initial concentrations of As (~1500 µg/L), Ni (~970 µg/L) and Zn (96,000 µg/L) were successfully reduced after organic substrate addition and pH correction to concentrations below the regulatory limits in Flanders (20 µg/L for As; 40 µg/L for Ni and 500 µg/L for Zn; VLAREBO, 2008). The formation of a black precipitate (iron sulfides) was observed both in the batch and the column studies. Metal(loid) removal in batch reactors (120 mL) was achieved after 4 weeks, whereas it took about >4 months in the column set-up to reach anoxic conditions and observed formation of sulfide precipitates. Based on the positive results from the treatability tests, a pilot field study was planned for an area of approximately 30 m², specifically targeting the second fine sand layer at 8–9 m depth. The treatment involved injecting an emulsified oil suspension (EOS) and a pH-buffer of potassium bicarbonate using the SPIN® technology for low-permeable soils (Injectis, Belgium). Although SRB have a wide pH tolerance range, there was concern that SRB performance would be lower outside of their optimal 6–8 range. As a result, a pH correction was included for biostimulation along with the addition of organic substrate. The emulsified oil suspension was selected for field application in detriment of the substrates tested in the laboratory (lactate and

protamylase™), because higher retention by aquifer solids is expected for EOS than for other organic substrates (ESTCP, 2008). The surfaces of the aquifer gradually become coated with a thin layer of oil droplets that provide a carbon and electron donor source for long-term sustained microbial activity. The amount of emulsified oil injected was based on various factors including: i) an electron donor potential of 0.25 g H₂/ g of EOS, ii) recommended manufacturer dilution ratios for injection between 4:1 and 20:1 (water:EOS), and iii) expected retention of oil by the aquifer matrix between 0,001–0,0005 kg oil/kg matrix. Groundwater parameters and metal(loid) concentrations were monitored using a central 2-in. monitoring well, 8062 and two peripheral 1-in. monitoring wells (9001 and 9003). All three wells were filtered from 8 to 9 mbgl. Fig. 1a provides a visual representation of the monitoring locations. The peripheral wells 9001 and 9003 were approx. 3 m apart from the central well 8062. A total of two injections were performed. The first injection was performed at the end of May 2021 (M1 – month 1), while the second injection was conducted at the end of Sep 2021 (M5 – month 5). For the first injection a mixture of 25 kg of EOS and 25 kg of potassium bicarbonate was prepared with 250 L of water in an intermediate bulk container. The mixture was injected at the targeted depth using injection

points I1 and I2 (Fig. 1a and b). The second injection involved a mixture of 100 kg of EOS and 100 kg of potassium bicarbonate with 660 L of water. The second injection was performed because the desired impact was not achieved with the first injection. In this case, the injection occurred through points I5 and I6 (Fig. 1a and b). Based on DOC measurements after the second injection we estimate that the oil retention by the solid matrix was about 0,0015 kg oil /kg matrix. The impact of the substrate injections on metal(loid) concentrations and other groundwater parameters was monitored for 34 months. Monitoring of groundwater started at the end of April 2021 (T0 – time 0) and finished in February 2024 (M34 – month 34).

2.3. Groundwater sampling and analytical methods

Groundwater from the monitoring wells indicated above was sampled using low density polyethylene sampling tubing immersed at the corresponding depth and connected to an above-ground peristaltic pump (12 VCD Advanced, Eijkelkamp Soil & Water, NL). Sampling was performed by standard low-purging rate (0.1–0.15 L min⁻¹) until 2/3 of the well volume were purged and the field groundwater parameters

Fig. 1. (a) Site map including study area. (b) Cross-section of study site and vertical location of injection delivery.

stabilized (pH, electrical conductivity, dissolved oxygen, and redox potential) as measured by a calibrated multi-sensor (Horiba, Japan). The samples were then shipped to AL-West Agrolab Laboratories (Deventer, NL) for analysis. The standardized analytical methods used included: NEN-EN-ISO 17294-2:2006 for Fe; WAC/III/B/011 for As, Ni, Cu, Pb and Zn; WAC/III/D/050 for dissolved organic C, NEN 6608 for sulfide; NEN 6482 (1999) for Fe(II); WAC/III/A/006 for carbonate and bicarbonate; WAC/III/C/002 for sulfate, nitrate, nitrite and ammonium; and WAC/III/C/002 for orthophosphate. Fe(III) was determined as the difference between total Fe and Fe(II).

2.4. Mineralogical analysis

In February 2024 (M34), 34 months after the start of the pilot study, a final sampling event was conducted to collect groundwater for mineralogical analysis of suspended particles representative of precipitates from the three monitoring locations. Groundwater was collected in 1 L PE bottles filled to the top and cooled on ice. Samples were immediately transported to the Materia Nova Institute in Mons, Belgium. Suspended material was collected by centrifugation after removal of the supernatant and dried for further sample preparation. The local elemental composition of the precipitates was analyzed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) combined with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). For this purpose, the precipitate was deposited on a silicon wafer and the analysis was performed on different areas of the sample corresponding to small spots of a few microns. The analyses were performed using a Hitachi SU8020 SEM with a Thermo-scific Noran System 7 SDD for EDX, at a high voltage of 20 kV. For bulk mineralogical analysis by X-ray diffraction (XRD), samples were mounted on a zero background holder. Diffraction patterns were collected on a Panalytical Empyrean instrument using a Cu-K α source at 45 kV and 40 mA, from 10 to 90° 2 θ in 0.02° steps. For quantitative/qualitative determination of the elemental composition of the precipitates samples were mounted on a 2 μ m filter and analyzed via X-ray fluorescence (XRF) using an Oxford Maxxi5 instrument at 50 kV.

2.5. 2.4 Compound stable isotope analysis

Groundwater samples (1 L) for stable isotope analysis of sulfate were taken in May 2022 (M13) from the three monitoring wells 8062, 9001 and 9003, and shipped in a cooled box to the commercial isotope laboratory Isodetect (Leipzig, Germany). Sulfate was precipitated from the aqueous samples at pH 3 with barium hydroxide. The precipitate (BaSO₄) was filtered off and weighed into tin capsules.

The sulfur isotope ratio of sulfate was determined using an elemental analyzer in combination with an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (EA3000 Eurovector, IRMS Isoprime micromass). For this, sulfate was oxidized to sulfur dioxide in the presence of oxygen at 1010 °C. For calibration of the raw data the international reference standards (IAEA-S1 $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{VCDT}} = -0.3 \text{ ‰}$; IAEA-S2 $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{VCDT}} = +22.6 \text{ ‰}$; IAEA-S3 $\delta^{34}\text{S}_{\text{VCDT}} = -32.5 \text{ ‰}$) and an internally calibrated laboratory standard (cysteine) were used ($n = 12$ at the start of each run and $n = 4$ after every 12 samples). The oxygen isotope ratio of sulfate was determined using an elemental analyzer in combination with an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (EA3000 Eurovector, IRMS Isoprime micromass). For this purpose, high-temperature pyrolysis at 1530 °C was performed. The international reference standards (IAEA-601 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{VSMOW}} = +23.14 \text{ ‰}$; IAEA-602 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{VSMOW}} = +71.28 \text{ ‰}$; USGS-54 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{VSMOW}} = +17.79 \text{ ‰}$) and an internally calibrated laboratory standard (dihydroxyanthraquinone) were used to calibrate the raw data ($n = 8$ at the beginning of each run and $n = 6$ at regular intervals). Additional information regarding isotope calculations is provided in the supplementary material (Text S3).

2.6. Nucleic acid extraction and purification

Groundwater intended for genomic DNA (gDNA) analysis was collected in sterilized 1 L polyethylene bottles, filled to the brim, sealed and doubled bagged to prevent oxygen diffusion into the sample, and shipped to Materia Nova Research Centre (Mons, Belgium). Upon arrival, the samples were stored overnight at 4 °C until processed for gDNA extraction. Samples were filtered through Sterivex™ (Millipore, MA) (0.22 μ m pore size) filters using a centrifugal pump and dual-trap system (see Text S3 of the SI for additional information on the volumes filtered). Filters were subsequently stored at -80 °C until further processing. For gDNA extraction the casing of the filter was opened, and the filter cut in approx. 30 pieces of similar size. Tubes containing the samples were vortexed horizontally for 10 min at 2700 rpm (Vortex-Genie® 2, Scientific Industries Inc., NY) to disrupt cells. DNA extraction was performed using UltraClean® Soil DNA Isolation Kit, (MO BIO Laboratories, CA) following the manufacturer's instructions. Elution of nucleic acids from the silica membrane was performed using 50 μ L of UltraPure™ DNase/RNase-Free Distilled Water (Invitrogen, CA).

2.7. Amplicon and shotgun sequencing

Extracted and purified DNA was sent to Novogene (UK) for both 16S rDNA amplicon and shotgun sequencing. 16S rDNA amplicon sequencing of the hypervariable region V4-V5 was performed for a total of 18 samples using the primer pair 515F 5'-GTGCCAGCMGCCGCGG-TAA-3' and 907R 5'-CCGTC AATTCCTTTGAGTTT-3'. PCR reactions were carried out with 15 μ L of Phusion® High - Fidelity PCR Master Mix (New England Biolabs), 0.2 μ M of forward and reverse primers, and about 10 ng template DNA. Thermal cycling consisted of initial denaturation at 98 °C for 1 min, followed by 30 cycles of denaturation at 98 °C for 10s, annealing at 50 °C for 30s, elongation at 72 °C for 30s, and final elongation at 72 °C for 5 min. PCR products of the proper size were selected through 2 % agarose gel electrophoresis. The same amount of PCR products from each sample was pooled, end-repaired, A-tailed, further ligated with Illumina adapters, and purified with Universal DNA Purification Kit (TianGen, China). Sequencing libraries were generated using NEB Next® Ultra™ II FS DNA PCR-free Library Prep Kit (New England Biolabs, USA) following manufacturer's recommendations, and indexes were added. The library was checked with Qubit and real-time PCR for quantification and bioanalyzer for size distribution detection. Quantified libraries were pooled and sequenced on Illumina platforms to generate 250 bp paired-end raw reads.

Shotgun metagenomic sequencing was performed for a total of 6 samples (M7 and M13 for each well). The genomic DNA was randomly sheared into fragments. The obtained fragments were end repaired, A-tailed, and further ligated with Illumina adapters. The fragments with adapters were size-selected, PCR amplified, and purified with Universal DNA Purification Kit (TianGen, China). Sequencing libraries were generated using NEB Next® Ultra™ II FS DNA PCR-free Library Prep Kit (New England Biolabs, USA) following manufacturer's recommendations and indexes were added. The library was checked with Qubit and real-time PCR for quantification and bioanalyzer for size distribution detection. Quantified libraries were pooled and sequenced on Illumina platforms to generate 150 bp paired-end raw reads.

2.8. Bioinformatic analysis

Amplicon sequence variants were called with the dada2 pipeline (Callahan et al., 2016). Beta diversity analysis was carried out via phyloseq (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013) using a canonical analysis of principal coordinates (CAP) ordination based on weighted unifrac distances. The phylogenetic tree for unifrac distance calculation was constructed using RAXML-NG (Kozlov et al., 2019). The metagenomes were assembled using the SqueezeMeta pipeline (Tamames and Puente-Sánchez, 2019) and analysis of the metagenomes was carried out using

SQMTools (Puente-Sánchez et al., 2020).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Field groundwater parameters

Dynamics for groundwater field parameters differed significantly among the three wells except for the temperature (Tables S12-S14). Groundwater temperature remained relatively constant over time with average values between 13.3 and 13.6 °C. The first injection in M1 had no impact on the main monitoring well 8062 as indicated by groundwater parameters between M3 and M4. After the second injection (M5), pH increased significantly from 4.4 to 5.9 and remained fairly constant until the end of the monitoring period (M34) (Fig. 2a and Table S12). The increase in pH observed in M6 was accompanied by a change in bicarbonate concentrations in 8062, from <3 mg/L to 360 mg/L. Bicarbonate concentration ranged between 150 and 330 mg/L for the rest of the study (Table S9). A significant change in redox potential was also recorded in well 8062 after the second injection in M5. The redox potential decreased from 157 mV (oxic) at T0 to -148 mV (anoxic) in M6 and remained between -200 mV and -400 mV thereafter (Fig. 2a). The change in redox conditions, as indicated by the decrease in redox potential, became evident only after the second addition of organic substrate in M5, after which dissolved organic carbon (DOC) increased from 5 mg/L to 100 mg/L in M6. However, DOC levels decreased to 10 mg/L after a further four months (M10) and stayed low until M34 (Table S12). The redox potential remained very negative, characteristic of strictly anoxic conditions, even after the apparent depletion of the organic substrate in groundwater. The dissolved oxygen concentrations for well 8062 remained consistently low, with values typically characteristic of anoxic conditions, i.e., 0.2 mg/L or less, throughout the study (Table S12). The low groundwater velocity and the inherently slow pore volume exchange with fresh and more oxic groundwater may also have contributed to this phenomenon.

In the case of the peripheral monitoring well 9001, a significant change in pH was observed after the first injection in M1. The pH increased from 5.0 at T0 up to 7.7 units in M3 and decreased to 5.7 by M6 (Fig. 2b). From M6 until the end of the study the pH remained relatively constant around 5.5. Significant increases in bicarbonate concentrations were observed after both the first and second injections. However, no additional effect on groundwater pH was observed after the second injection when bicarbonate concentrations peaked at 180 mg/L.

Bicarbonate concentrations gradually decreased to approximately 30 mg/L by the end of the study (Table S13). In contrast to the main monitoring well 8062, the redox potential in well 9001 became less oxic after the first injection, with a net change from 155 to 39 mV. However, no further reduction in redox potential was recorded in the following months for well 9001, except for M27 (Fig. 2b). The range of DOC concentrations for this well varied between 4 and a maximum of 25 mg/L in M7, suggesting that the organic substrate did not impact this peripheral location as effectively as it did in the case of well 8062. Dissolved oxygen remained stable at concentrations between 0.1 and 0.3 mg/L throughout the study (Table S13).

For well 9003, no significant changes were observed for any of the field groundwater parameters and DOC, except for redox (Fig. 2c and Table S14). Redox potential fluctuations between M11 and M27, alternating between positive and negative values, are not consistent with previous measurements or values for other parameters at this location (e.g. DOC and dissolved O₂). The direct influence of anoxic groundwater from the upstream well 8062, a few meters away, towards the second half of the monitoring period, cannot be excluded.

Overall, the dynamics of the field groundwater parameters indicate that the distribution of organic substrate and the bicarbonate was heterogeneous among the three locations studied. The results for the central well 8062 are consistent with optimal delivery of both substances, but only after the second injection. For the peripheral well 9001, the increase in bicarbonate concentrations after both the first and second injections indicates successful distribution. This was not the case for the organic substrate, with only a slight increase of DOC in M7. Finally, none of the substances incorporated seemed to reach sufficiently the peripheral well 9003 in any of the injection campaigns.

3.2. Metal(loid) and sulfate concentrations

Metal(loid) concentrations in well 8062 gradually decreased after the second injection in M5 and remained relatively low throughout the monitoring period (Figs. 2d). By M8, the original concentration of Zn, which was around 80,000 µg/L, had decreased to 6 µg/L. Similarly, the concentration of Ni had changed from around 300 µg/L to approximately 5 µg/L by M9. There was also a significant decrease in As concentrations, from 2000 to 2500 µg/L to 15 µg/L by M12. These concentrations are below the Flemish regulatory threshold for groundwater (Table S1) and the changes observed represent a removal of almost 100 % for As and Zn, and 98 % for Ni. These results were

Fig. 2. Groundwater parameters and metal removal results at each monitoring well: (a,d) 8062, (b,e) 9001, (c,f) 9003. Arrows indicate substrate injections.

consistent with changes in total Fe, which decreased from approximately 76,000 $\mu\text{g/L}$ to 7200 $\mu\text{g/L}$ by M11, and sulfate concentrations, which decreased from 800 mg/L to approximately 500 mg/L by M8 (Fig. 2a). The detection of sulfide at concentrations ranging from 5 up to 17 mg/L between M9 and M19, and even in M34, provides additional evidence of biological sulfidogenic processes in well 8062 (Table S12).

These results suggest that As, Ni, and Zn precipitated either as pure sulfides or co-precipitated with iron sulfides as a result of SRB biostimulation (Peltier et al., 2011; Sun et al., 2016; Pi et al., 2017). For As, both biogenic formation of pure arsenic sulfides including realgar (As_2S_3) and orpiment (As_2S_3) (Le Pape et al., 2017) and arsenopyrite (FeAsS) (Rittle et al., 1995; Onstott et al., 2011) have been demonstrated in laboratory experiments using SRB consortia. However, in the presence of iron, Saunders et al. (2018) confirmed through microscopic and X-ray diffraction analyses that pyrite was the only iron-sulfide formed and that no arsenic-only sulfide phase precipitated. In addition, those authors suggest that under reducing groundwater conditions, pH in the range 5 to 8 and the low temperatures encountered in groundwater, arsenian pyrite rather than arsenopyrite should be the dominant arsenic-bearing iron sulfide. The residual As concentrations observed in well 8062 were in the range reported previously for SRB treatment of contaminated water in laboratory experiments (Keimowitz et al., 2007; Onstott et al., 2011). For Ni, precipitation as discrete Ni sulfides rather than co-precipitation with Fe-sulfides has been described as the main mechanism for Ni removal in anoxic and sulfidic environments (Ferris et al., 1987; Mansor and Fantle, 2019). In laboratory experiments, Peltier et al. (2011) showed that the formation of biogenic ZnS was not affected by the presence of dissolved Fe(II). Therefore, it is expected that a significant fraction of Zn was removed as pure zinc-sulfide at our site. Prior the onset of strictly anoxic conditions in well 8062, iron was mainly present in the reduced form Fe(II) accounting for approx. 85 % of the total iron. After the second injection, from M7 to M19, all iron present was Fe(II). The changes in total iron were also reflected in the dynamics of Fe(II) concentrations. An increase in total Fe and Fe(II) concentrations was observed after M12. The mass balance of total Fe and Fe(II) also suggests the presence of Fe(III) after M23. At the end of the study, Fe concentrations reached values between 18,000–40,000 $\mu\text{g/L}$, i.e. less than half of the initial concentration. For Ni, a less pronounced increase to 79–85 $\mu\text{g/L}$, or 23 % of the initial concentration, was observed for M27 and M30. However, the concentration measured at the end of the study in M34 was 26 $\mu\text{g/L}$, approximately 10 % of the initial concentration (Fig. 2d). The As concentrations measured in M27–M30 at 21 $\mu\text{g/L}$ still represented a negligible percentage (<1 %) of the initial concentration. The value of 4.5 $\mu\text{g/L}$ measured in M34 indicates further stability of As precipitates. Zinc concentrations were still below the method detection limit at the end of the study (Fig. 2d). These results suggest a different stability of the metal(loid) sulfide precipitates or co-precipitates formed as compared to iron. These results are also consistent with the removal efficiencies observed in the batch study where strictly anoxic conditions were achieved (Table S5 in the Supplementary Material).

For well 9001, there was a significant drop in metal(loid) and Fe concentrations after the first injection, between T0 and M3. Arsenic concentrations decreased rapidly from 4600 to 730 $\mu\text{g/L}$, Ni from 1000 to 300 $\mu\text{g/L}$ and Zn from 120,000 $\mu\text{g/L}$ to 31,000 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Fig. 2e). However, the low concentrations observed in well 8062 after the second injection were not reached here. A significant decrease was also observed for total Fe from 59,000 to 19,000 $\mu\text{g/L}$ and for sulfate from 1000 to 440 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Table S13 and Fig. 2b). Iron(II) concentrations also decreased from 50 to 10 mg/L and Fe(III) concentrations from 9 to <0.1 mg/L (Table S2). These results suggest that SRB activity and metal(loid) (co)precipitation occurred after the first injection at this peripheral location. Interestingly, changes in DOC concentrations were minimal and sulfide remained below the detection limit of the method, in contrast to what was observed in well 8062 after the second injection. From M4, there was a gradual increase in metal(loid), sulfate, Fe(II) and Fe(III) concentrations over subsequent months. Towards the end of the

monitoring period, values in the range of the initial concentrations at T0 were observed. These data suggest that the initial injection had only a short-term effect on metal(loid) removal. Despite the significant decrease in sulfate concentrations, it is possible that metal(loid) precipitation as hydroxide or bicarbonate salts, both of which are more sensitive to pH changes and therefore more susceptible to redissolution than sulfide salts, may have contributed significantly to metal(loid) removal in 9001 (Lewis, 2010). Here, the pH increased rapidly from <5 in T0 to 7.7 in M3, 1.5 units more than the maximum pH reached in 8062. In addition, the redox potential remained positive in 9001, suggesting that the strictly anoxic conditions achieved in 8062, better suited for SRB activity, were not met here.

For well 9003, there were no consistent changes in metal(loid), sulfate, sulfide, Fe(II) and Fe(III) concentrations indicative of SRB activity or metal(loid) precipitation/co-precipitation (Figs. 2c and f, and Table S14). A moderate decrease in sulfate and metal(loid) concentrations along with negative redox potential was observed from M10 to M19 (Figs. 2c and f). However, these results do not correspond to increased DOC or bicarbonate concentrations in this well, which would indicate adequate substrate delivery to this peripheral location. Thus, an influence of groundwater from 8062, upstream of 9003, in the later phase of the study cannot be ruled out.

3.3. Mineralogical analysis

To gain insight into the potential mineral phases formed in the aquifer at both the central and peripheral monitoring wells, a final groundwater sampling event was conducted in month 34 (M34). In the field, a significant difference was observed between the groundwater from the central (8062) and peripheral monitoring wells (9001 and 9003): groundwater collected from the central monitoring well contained a significant amount of black suspended particles, whereas groundwater from the peripheral wells was apparently clear. The visual differences between the three locations became even more apparent in the laboratory, particularly in the preparation for XRD analysis (Figs. 3 and 4). Samples from central monitoring well 8062 were characterized by an intense black color typical of FeS formed under anoxic conditions (Hue: N; Value:1.5 and Chroma: 0). In contrast, samples from the peripheral monitoring wells exhibited brown-ochre (9001; Hue: 10YR; Value:6 and Chroma: 8) and brown-reddish (9003; Hue: 2.5YR; Value:4 and Chroma: 6) hues characteristic of iron-oxide minerals, with yellowish hues being more representative of hydrated iron oxides than reddish hues (Gupta et al., 2008).

Images obtained by SEM revealed the presence of amorphous precipitates and rather lack of crystals in all samples analyzed for all three locations. The dominance of amorphous minerals is evident from the XRD spectra with no apparent identifiable peaks (Figs. 4b, d and f). Only a small peak is observed at an angle of 2 theta between 20 and 30 (Fig. 4d), but the resolution was not sufficient for identification. Structurally disordered materials cannot be identified by XRD. However, the unresolved diffraction spectra showed distinct intensity signals at different 2 theta angles, suggesting the presence of different mineral phases in the three samples. The high oxygen content detected in all samples and areas analyzed by SEM-EDX with a relative abundance of about 30–50 % (Figs. 3a, b and c) suggests the presence of water in the precipitates, which is indicative of hydrous mineral phases (Rimsaite, 1979). SEM-EDX data also suggest a distinct composition of the precipitates from the three samples. In the central monitoring well (8062), precipitates with up to 18 % S and 19 % Ca were detected, as well as precipitates with up to 30–35 % Cl, 12 % Na and Fe (Fig. 3a). In contrast, the Fe content in precipitates from peripheral monitoring wells 9001 and 9003, with a relative abundance between 13 and 30 %, was significantly higher than in 8062. The S content in 9001 and 9003 ranged from 5 to 10 %. Data from 9001 and 9003 also showed the presence of 5–10 % Zn and As 1.5–6 % and even 1 % Cu in 9001. Nickel was not detected by SEM-EDX, but was clearly present in all samples

8062 (central monitoring well)

	C	O	Na	Mg	Al	S	Cl	K	Ca	Mn	Fe
<i>Image 1_pt1</i>	1.5	48.1	2.0	0.5	5.4	17.7	3.2	1.1	18.7	/	1.7
<i>Image 2_pt2</i>	2.3	26.3	11.8	1.4	5.6	3.5	34.6	0.6	0.3	1.0	12.6
<i>Image 3_pt3</i>	2.4	29.2	13.4	1.8	6.4	3.0	30.7	0.6	0.2	0.5	11.9

9001 (peripheral monitoring well)

	C	O	Mg	Al	S	Cl	K	Ca	Ti	Fe	Cu	Zn	As
<i>Image 6_pt1</i>	1.9	45.4	1.3	1.3	4.6	3.9	0.2	0.5	/	27.9	1.3	5.7	5.9
<i>Image 6_pt2</i>	1.6	45.2	1.3	1.3	4.8	4.3	0.2	0.4	/	28.9	1.3	5.4	5.3
<i>Image 6_pt3</i>	1.3	50.3	1.9	0.6	9.0	6.3	0.5	1.2	0.3	18.5	/	5.5	4.6

9003 (peripheral monitoring well)

	C	O	Mg	Al	S	Cl	K	Ca	Fe	Zn	As
<i>Image 8_pt1</i>	1.6	48.3	1.3	0.6	8.4	5.6	0.7	2.0	24.9	5.2	1.5
<i>Image 8_pt2</i>	1.4	51.2	2.3	/	11.0	10.4	0.6	/	13.4	9.7	/
<i>Image 8_pt3</i>	1.3	47.6	1.9	0.8	10.0	5.9	1.0	3.1	23.4	5.0	/

Fig. 3. Samples and particle analyses by SEM-EDX for precipitates obtained from the central well 8062 (a and b) and the peripheral monitoring wells 9001 (c and d) and 9003 (e and f).

Fig. 4. Results and samples for XRF and XRD analyses for precipitates obtained from the central well 8062 (a and b) and the peripheral monitoring wells 9001 (c and d) and 9003 (e and f).

according to XRF analysis (Fig. 4a, b and c). Along with Ni, significant peaks for Fe and Zn were detected by XRF. The presence of As was also detected in 9001 and 9003, but with a significantly lower peak intensity compared to the metals. According to other studies, SRB activity generally results in the formation of metastable Fe sulfides such as amorphous FeS rather than crystalline forms (Suthersan et al., 2009; Berg et al., 2020). Based on isotopic signatures ($\delta^{56}\text{Fe}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$) in sedimentary pyrites, it has been suggested that pyritization may be driven by a combination of abiotic processes (diagenesis) and microbial Fe and S reduction (Archer and Vance, 2006; Guilbaud et al., 2011; Jia et al., 2023). Formation of Fe sulfides in SRB cultures has been demonstrated in the laboratory; mackinawite (FeS) and greigite (Fe_3S_4) were the dominant Fe-sulfide phases formed according to Gramp et al. (2010). The authors reported that increasing the incubation temperature from 22 to 60 °C significantly enhanced the crystallinity of the Fe sulfides after incubation times of up to 16 weeks. This temperature range is significantly higher than the temperatures measured in the groundwater during our pilot study (13–15 °C). In other laboratory studies where the formation of metal(loid) sulfides has been reported, incubation temperatures are also expected to be around 22 °C (Keimowitz et al., 2007;

Onstott et al., 2011; Peltier et al., 2011; Saunders et al., 2018). Thus, under the natural conditions found at the study site (13–15 °C) with a groundwater temperature range common for Central Europe, the formation of crystalline metal(loid) sulfides is limited and may require significantly longer times.

3.4. Compound specific isotope analysis (CSIA) of sulfate

During the last two decades Compound Specific Isotope Analysis (CSIA) has become an indispensable approach to study biotic and even abiotic transformations of both organic and inorganic compounds in groundwater environments (USEPA, 2008; Davidson et al., 2009; Mundle et al., 2012; Lihl et al., 2019; Pelerin et al., 2019; Schwab et al., 2023). Under anoxic conditions, dissimilatory sulfate-reducing bacteria (SRB) can use sulfate as an electron acceptor, which is subsequently reduced to sulfide. Because biochemical reactions favor the light isotopes (^{32}S and ^{16}O) over the heavy isotopes (^{34}S and ^{18}O), the heavy ^{34}S and potentially the heavy ^{18}O isotopes accumulate in the remaining pool of untransformed sulfate molecules. As a result, the stable isotope signatures $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ and/or $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of sulfate become increasingly positive (Antler

et al., 2013). Accordingly, the lowest (less positive) isotope signatures of the three wells were identified for well 9001. Consequently, the isotopic signature of well 9001 was considered as source or reference for measuring potential changes in isotope signatures due to SRB activity in the other two wells. The $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ and/or $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ isotopic signatures are typically used to determine the sources and cycling of sulfate and sulfur and/or evaluate the transformation of SO_4^{2-} (Sun et al., 2017; Jiang et al., 2022). For well 9001, the $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ was +6.1 ‰ and the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ 13.9 ‰. These values are characteristic of evaporite salts or soluble salts including those reported in pyrite-rich mining wastes (Li et al., 2013; Wang and Zhang, 2019; Tabelin et al., 2020 and 2022). The elevated sulfate concentrations at the site are related to oxidation of sulfuric acid that was historically spilled along with metal(loid) and iron-rich acidic solution. The CSIA measurements conducted in M13 for the two peripheral monitoring locations 9001 and 9003 and the central monitoring well 8062 showed significant changes for $\delta^{34}\text{S}$, but not for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$. The $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ isotopic signature of sulfate ranged from +6.1 ‰ in well 9001 to +16.3 ‰ in 8062 (Table 1). In contrast, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ isotopic signatures were relatively similar among the three wells with values ranging from +13.9 ‰ in well 9001 to +14.7 ‰ in 8062 (Table 1). To quantify the sulfate reduction process, isotope enrichment factors for S (ϵ_s) in the range -14.8 and -6.2 ‰ were used, which were previously reported for microorganisms in environments where no significant change in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ was observed (Turchyn et al., 2010). Based on these constraints, the extent of the sulfate reduction was estimated to be 49–80 % for the 8062 sample and 25–50 % for the 9003 sample (Table 1). For well 9001, used as reference, there would be no sulfate reduction. The data for 8062 are consistent with the changes and situation observed in field groundwater parameters, metal(loid), sulfate and sulfide in this well in M13. This is also the case for well 9001, with possible evidence for SRB activity after the first injection, but gradual recovery of baseline conditions after M6. Finally, CSIA results for well 9003, suggest moderate SRB activity in this location, which is in line with the limited decrease in metal(loid) and sulfate concentrations, as well as the negative redox potential measurements between M10 and M19 in this location. A partial mixing with groundwater from 8062, ~3 m upstream of 9003, cannot be discarded given the duration of the study.

3.5. Dynamic changes in microbial community composition

The groundwater was sampled to investigate changes in the microbial community composition up until M13 for well 8062 and M9 for wells 9001 and 9003. Canonical analysis of principal coordinates (CAP) revealed the temporal dynamics of microbial community composition in each monitoring well (Fig. 5). In well 9003, the community exhibited a shift in composition from T0 to M5. However, beyond M5, only relatively modest changes were observed, which are consistent with the stable groundwater parameters at this location observed throughout the study. On the other hand, wells 9001 and 8062 displayed dynamic changes in community composition after T0 and M5, respectively, which coincides with the first and second injections. This data is consistent with changes in groundwater parameters and metal(loid) concentrations observed for these wells. Axis CAP1 of the beta-diversity ordination plot accounts for ~45 % of variation within the samples. On the other hand,

Table 1

Summary of compound specific isotope analysis results performed in month 13 for three monitoring wells (9001, 9003 and 8062).

Monitoring well	9001	9003	8062
$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ in mg/L (T0)	1000	660	800
$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ in mg/L (M13)	980	660	620
$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{min}}$ in mg/L (month)	440 (M3)	580 (M9)	450 (M9)
$\delta^{34}\text{S}$ ‰ (M13)	+6.1	+10.4	+16.3
$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ ‰ (M13)	+13.9	+14.4	+14.7
Net change in $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ ‰	-	+4.3	+10.2
Estimated fraction of SO_4^{2-} reduced	-	0.3–0.5	0.5–0.8

Fig. 5. Canonical analysis of principal coordinates (CAP) based on a weighted unifrac distance. Timepoints are connected by arrows depicting the development of the microbial community over time. The grey vectors depict the correlation of environmental parameters (pH, redox potential) and metal(loid) and sulfate removal outcomes with specific samples.

axis CAP2 accounts for only ~6 % of the variation. Thus, it is apparent that wells 9003 and 8062 underwent significant changes in composition, albeit in opposite directions, while well 9001 exhibited similar changes to the main monitoring well (8062), only less pronounced. In addition, the ordination analysis accounts for environmental parameters (pH and redox potential) as well as changes in metal(loid) concentration compared to T0. As revealed in Fig. 5, the microbial community in well 8062 after M6 and in well 9001 in M5 and M9 are similar in composition. Moreover, the populations in those samples are associated with a higher pH, lower redox potential, and improved metal(loid) and sulfate removal.

The dynamic composition of the microbial community throughout the experiment is displayed in Fig. 6. At the phylum level, in the main monitoring well 8062 associated with metal removal, we observed the proliferation of *Firmicutes* and other anaerobe harboring taxa such as *Bacteroidota* and *Spirochaetes* that have previously been detected in organically biostimulated aquifers (Pérez-de-Mora et al., 2014b), at the expense of *Proteobacteria*. At the level of the lowest taxonomic rank assigned to amplicon sequence variants, this change mostly corresponds to the decline of *Gallionella* (phylum *Proteobacteria*), a chemolithotrophic iron oxidizer which does not grow in anoxic conditions and exists at microaerobic gradients (Hallbeck and Pedersen, 1990; Hallbeck and Pedersen, 2015), initially present with high abundance, followed by the successive proliferation of *Desulfosporosinus* (phylum *Firmicutes*) during M7–13. *Desulfosporosinus* is a strictly anaerobic, acidophilic SRB (Hippe and Stackebrandt, 2015), able to grow autotrophically, utilising H_2 and CO or CO_2 via the Wood-Ljungdahl pathway (Valeria et al., 2020), while also capable to grow heterotrophically on fatty acids (Klemp et al., 1985). Thus, this taxon is able to partake in the degradation of the EOS used as a substrate in this pilot, while it is also able to proliferate via autotrophic metabolism and sulfate reduction even when the substrate is apparently depleted, thereby sustaining long-term sulfate-reduction.

Our sampling captured the succession of microbial communities in well 8062 after the second injection (M5). *Gallionella* (chemolithotrophic iron-oxidiser) was initially succeeded by a heterotrophic community (M6), before the subsequent establishment of *Desulfosporosinus* (mixotrophic sulfate reducer). In M6, the most abundant taxa were *Undibacterium* (21 %), *Oxalobacteraceae* (20 %), *Gallionella* (13 %),

Fig. 6. Changes in microbial community composition in the three monitoring wells.

Clostridium sensu stricto 1 (7 %), *Enterobacteriaceae* (4 %), *Comamonadaceae* (3 %) and *Rhodospirillum* (1 %). The family *Oxalobacteraceae* and genus *Undibacterium* belong to the same family of aerobic bacteria that have previously been found associated with alkane degradation (Wang et al., 2016), while the same is true for the family *Comamonadaceae* (Sun et al., 2017), suggesting that these taxa could be responsible for the oxidation of the fatty acids found in EOS, since fatty acids and alkanes share the same catabolic pathways. In addition, *Clostridium* are anaerobic fermentative bacteria, which are known to degrade fatty acids (Hatamoto et al., 2007).

After M6, the heterotrophic community was succeeded by a community dominated by the sulfate-reducing *Desulfosporosinus*, apparent between M7–13 (Fig. 6), which correlated with the establishment of anoxic conditions in this well (Fig. 2a). The proliferation of *Desulfosporosinus*, in combination with metal(loid) removal in the main monitoring well and one of the peripheral wells during T0–M13 (Fig. 2d–e), suggest that microbial sulfate reduction and subsequent metal(loid) (co-)precipitation was driven by this genus. In addition, in the main monitoring well (8062) where *Desulfosporosinus* was the most abundant, we detected amorphous FeS minerals at the end of the study. The formation of FeS phases such as greigite at the action of *Desulfosporosinus* has been described in the pH range 4.5–6 (Bertel et al., 2012), which matches the pH levels in the aquifers upon pH correction.

In the case of the peripheral wells (9001 and 9003), the dynamic microbial succession was not captured by our sampling, as the first sample after the initial injection was taken in M5. At this point, well 9001 was already dominated by *Desulfosporosinus* (42 %), although the second most abundant taxon was *Oxalobacteraceae* (5 %), suggesting that the bloom of *Oxalobacteraceae* might have occurred after the first injection between M1 to M5. The peripheral well 9003 was dominated by *Gallionella* throughout the experiment after T0. In the case of well 9003, oxic conditions were present for most part of the study along with elevated iron concentrations in the groundwater, explaining the dominance of *Gallionella* at this location, and further substantiating the observation that the organic substrate did not reach this location.

The change to less oxic conditions in well 9001 after the first injection (M1) and to strictly anoxic conditions in well 8062 after the second injection (M6), as evidenced by the respective shift to less positive redox

potential for 9001 and to negative redox potential for 8062, was likely caused by additional respiratory oxygen depletion upon aerobic utilization of the substrate by the heterotrophic community. Changes in the microbial composition thereafter in both monitoring wells, specifically the enrichment of *Desulfosporosinus* reflect the drastic change in the groundwater from iron-oxidizing to sulfate-reducing conditions in both wells. Under anoxic conditions, competition between sulfate-reduction and iron-reduction is possible, since sulfate reducers may also directly reduce Fe(III) (Coleman et al., 1993). However, sulfate is in large excess in the groundwater (500–100 mg/L), whereas Fe (III) is present in much lower concentrations (10–20 mg/L) (Tables S12–14). After the second injection, the concentration of Fe(III) decreased from 7 mg/L to <0.1 mg/L, whereas the sulfate concentration decreased from 820 to 640 mg/L, indicating both iron and sulfate reduction taking place. After M6, the availability of Fe(III) became limiting, whereas the supply of sulfate was still in excess, allowing sulfate reduction to be the primary respiratory activity. Established sulfate-reducing processes at the expense of iron-reducing processes is also highlighted by the fact that Fe(II) concentration decreased while sulfide concentration increased in Months 6–23 due to the formation of iron sulfides in the central monitoring well 8062 (Table S12). With regards to competition of sulfate reducers with methanogens for hydrogen as the electron source, we did not detect significant numbers of *Archaea* (data not shown) nor methanogenic bacteria in our samples. It has been shown that methanogenesis in a shallow anoxic aquifer was inhibited below pH 7 (Beeman and Sulflita, 1990), therefore the slightly acidic conditions in the groundwater is expected to inhibit the proliferation of methanogens.

3.6. Detection of dissimilatory sulfate reduction (DSR) genes in groundwater metagenomes

Metagenome sequencing was carried out on gDNA extracted from the groundwater at M7 and M13 as extracts of other timepoints did not have sufficient gDNA. Through analysis of the metagenomes, we quantified DSR genes within the groundwater at M7 and M13, namely adenylyl:sulfate transferase (*sat*), adenylyl-sulfate reductase (*aprAB*), dissimilatory sulfite reductase (*dsrAB*), and anaerobic sulfate reductase (*asrABC*) (Fig. S3). Those genes were present in all samples, but in

different quantities. Wells 8062 and 9003 harbored an increased proportion of DSR genes compared to well 9001. This was unexpected, as well 9003 did not exhibit anoxic conditions or consistent sulfate reduction and/or metal(loid) removal as observed for 8062, nor did it develop an ecology dominated by SRB like wells 9001 and 8062. For well 9001, the low presence of DSR genes for the two timepoints considered here, M7 and M13, coincides with a period of increased metal(loid) concentrations, during which the original contaminant levels from T0 were reached after an initial drop following the first injection. This suggests a short-term effect of the first injection here and that the substrates added did not reach this location after the second injection. On the other hand, the higher DSR gene count in well 8062 in M7 and M13 corresponds to significant sulfate reduction and metal(loid) s removal from the groundwater after the second injection.

In order to reveal the major contributors to the DSR pathway within the microbial community, taxonomic classification of DSR genes was performed. In well 8062, the main contributors were *Desulfosporosinus*, *Desulfobacteraceae*, and *Desulfobacterales* (Fig. 7). The proportion of DSR genes harbored by *Desulfosporosinus* in well 8062 was especially high, particularly in M7, whereas the relative contribution of DSR genes harbored by *Desulfobacteraceae* and *Desulfobacterales* increased in M13. This change was also reflected in the relative contribution of dissimilatory sulfite reductases (*dsrAB*) vs adenylylsulfate reductases (*aprAB*), which increased from M7 to M13 (Fig. S3). Although at much lower abundance, *Desulfosporosinus* also contributes to the DSR pathway in wells 9001 and 9003. In fact, despite the lower proportion of DSR genes in the metagenome of well 9001, a large fraction of those genes is contributed by *Desulfosporosinus*. However, in contrast to 8062 and 9001, the taxonomic assignment in well 9003 indicates the presence of a very different DSR harboring community dominated by unclassified *Nitrosomonadales* followed by unclassified *Delta-* and *Betaproteobacteria*. DSR genes originating from the order *Nitrosomonadales* are likely contributed by *Gallionella* (the dominant taxon in well 9003), as this genus belongs to *Nitrosomonadales*, and is known to harbor DSR genes (Kadnikov et al., 2016). Since DSR genes can also function to oxidise sulfur (Pott and Dahl, 1998), the presence of the DSR pathway genes in iron-oxidiser *Gallionella* may in fact serve this purpose. Therefore, the elevated presence of DSR genes in well 9003 does not necessarily align with the metabolic capability to reduce sulfate. In well 9003, the presence of DSR genes harbored by non-SRB, in combination with the lack of DSR genes from *Desulfosporosinus*, *Desulfobacteraceae* and *Desulfobacteraceae* and the persistent oxic conditions in this well suggests that the estimated sulfate reduction of 25–50 % in this peripheral well (based on sulfate isotope ratios) may in fact be due to groundwater exchange between this well and the slightly upstream main monitoring well 8062 where biological sulfate reduction took place.

Fig. 7. Abundance and taxonomic classification of dissimilatory sulfate reduction (DSR) in each well metagenome.

3.7. Implications and perspectives for using in-situ biological precipitation

Metal(loid) contamination at hydrogeological settings with low to moderate groundwater flow is generally persistent and challenging to treat due to their limited subsurface hydraulics. Unlike organic contaminants, metal(loid)s cannot be destroyed or easily recovered from the subsurface. Thus, in-situ approaches to immobilize metal(loid)s permanently in the aquifer soil matrix provide an alternative to conventional (ex-situ) pump & treat strategies worth considering. For successful implementation of ISMP three main key factors need to be considered (Suthersan et al., 2009): i) the kinetics (meaningful rates of precipitation), ii) equilibrium solubility (meet required standards for groundwater), and iii) durability (stability of the precipitate over time). To the best of our knowledge this is the first time that these three criteria have been met in a real groundwater environmental setting for a time-frame of months/years. Within 2–3 months after the second substrate injection As, Ni and Zn concentrations in groundwater decreased below regulatory limits. The success of the treatment at the central location (8062) is still evident 29 months after the second organic substrate (electron donor) addition at month 5, even though dissolved organic C concentrations returned to original levels (5–10 mg/L) about 3 months later. A key to this success seems to be the stability of the groundwater conditions achieved both in terms of pH and redox potential. A moderately acidic pH of about 6 ± 0.2 units has been maintained at this location compared to the original more acidic conditions (approx. 4.5–5 units) and pH observed in the peripheral monitoring wells. At the same time, strictly anoxic conditions (redox potential of -400 mV) over the last two years may have prevented the action of sulfur and iron oxidizing microorganisms and sustained, at the same time, the activity of SRB. The presence of sulfide in groundwater from the central monitoring well 8062 is still evident both analytically and sensorially (smell of rotten eggs and presence of black precipitate). Thus, in hydrogeological environments with low to moderate groundwater velocity such as the present case, perspectives for long-term stability of ISMP treatment are promising. Similar situations are expected in alluvial sedimentary deposits in many other fluvial influenced areas. In aquifers with greater permeability and, hence, greater pore water volume exchange with fresh oxic groundwater, it may be more challenging to maintain strictly anoxic conditions. Nonetheless, delivery of organic substrate and, if necessary, pH-buffering agents to the target zone can be more efficient in coarser sediments. Thus, it is important to assess individually for each site the most suitable remedial strategies and compare various potential approaches. Pilot studies such as the current work provide a robust basis for cost-benefit analysis and evaluation for full scale implementation. As stable anoxic conditions were still maintained at the end of the study, the stability of the expected amorphous precipitates formed (including metal(loid) sulfides) formed remains open, should aquifer conditions change to an oxic environment. Evaluation of this phenomenon at the study site may be challenging. Sequential replacement of treated groundwater with fresh oxic, yet metal(loid) contaminated, groundwater would also imply a new input of contaminants to the area treated. Nonetheless, data obtained from the batch and column studies, suggest that re-solubilization of the metal(loid)s precipitated is limited even at high redox potential. It should be also noted that aerobic microbial activity (sulfur- and iron-oxidizing bacteria) at the study site may be discrete due to the low dissolved O_2 availability (concentrations of 0.1–0.3 mg/L) measured throughout the study for all three locations regardless of the redox potential. At the same time, SRB may be able to extend their activity beyond the active treatment period at low levels or limited donor availability as suggested by this study. Finally, long-term investigations on other metal(loid) impacted subsurface scenarios (e.g. with lower sulfate levels, more neutral pH conditions, other metal(loid)s and permeability and temperature conditions) are important to better assess and understand the potential of ISMP for aquifer treatment.

4. Conclusions

The integrative assessment approach used in this study, which combines long-term monitoring of physicochemical properties and metal(loid) concentrations with mineralogical, stable isotope and microbiological analyses, demonstrates that long-term precipitation of metal(loid)s present in the milligram per liter range as relatively stable amorphous mineral phases can be achieved in situ by stimulation of native SRB present in the subsurface. At the studied site, the sulfate-reducing process seems to be inhibited by persistent unfavourable conditions of the groundwater, such as low pH, lack of substrates for heterotrophic metabolism, and a microaerobic environment. Upon biostimulation and pH correction, we observed dynamic changes in the microbial community in the central monitoring well 8062, which in combination with the metagenome analysis revealed that sulfate reduction might have been primarily carried out by *Desulfosporosinus*. However, the activity was dependent on sufficient dispersal of the organic substrate as electron donor, as evidenced by unchanged groundwater parameters at peripheral well 9003, as well as the lack of development towards an active SRB-dominated microbial community structure and the persistence of the chemolithotrophic *Gallionella* at this location.

In the central monitoring well, changes in groundwater parameters after the second injection (increased pH and DOC and lower redox potential) were correlated with a shift in microbial community composition towards a sulfate-reducing community. The activity of the SRB was confirmed by a positive change in the 34S/32S stable isotope signature of sulfate, the detection of sulfide and a significant decrease in As, Ni and Zn concentrations below Flemish regulatory values. The decrease in metal(loid) concentrations was associated with the formation of insoluble metal(loid) sulfides. At the end of the study (month 34), groundwater sampled from the central monitoring well was characterized by a strong sulfide odor (confirmed analytically) and a black precipitate similar to that found in the batch and column study. Mineralogical analysis revealed the presence of amorphous minerals containing sulfur, iron, nickel and zinc. In contrast, in the peripheral monitoring wells, no sulfide odor was detected (and no sulfide was detected analytically) and the particulate amorphous material showed yellow-red hues typical of iron oxides and oxyhydroxides and a higher iron content than the precipitates in the central monitoring well. This observation is consistent with the iron-oxidizing conditions and microbial composition present in the peripheral monitoring wells.

The stability of the precipitates formed, even 30 months after the injection of the organic substrate, and under slightly acidic conditions (current pH of about 6), is remarkable, even though no crystalline sulfide minerals were observed. For contaminated sites that are also characterized by acidic groundwater conditions, increasing the pH may help to reduce remediation time frames and prolong system maintenance. In this case, the cost/benefit of buffering the system needs to be carefully evaluated. The fact that limited metal(loid) solubilization was observed during the column study, when metal(loid) precipitates were flushed with highly oxidic groundwater (redox of +400 mV) suggests that significant metal(loid) mobilization is not expected even if the aquifer returns to its original oxidic conditions (redox of +200 mV). The fact that metal(loid) concentrations remained very low despite the return of iron concentrations to initial values provides additional evidence of the stability of the precipitates formed. In addition, the limited oxygen availability in the aquifer (<0.3 mg/L) as compared to well-aerated aquifers (4–5 mg/L) should provide an additional protective effect against the activity of iron and sulfide oxidizing bacteria even at higher redox potential. Based on the maximum DOC concentrations measured in the groundwater, it is expected that a significant amount of the organic substrate was retained by the sediment. Thus, prolonged supply of organic C and electron donor may therefore help to sustain SRB activity even at apparently low levels of organic C. The removal rates achieved even at low groundwater temperatures (13–15 °C) further

highlight the potential of this approach for full-scale application at a wide range of latitudes.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Alfredo Pérez-de-Mora: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Herwig de Wilde:** Project administration, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dirk Paulus:** Project administration, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Stephanie Roosa:** Investigation. **Rob Onderwater:** Investigation. **Yoann Paint:** Investigation. **Claudio Avignone Rossa:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Daniel Farkas:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Table S1: Regulatory values in Flanders for soil and groundwater; Table S2-S4: Physico-chemical properties of soil and groundwater; Text S1: Treatability tests (batch); Text S2, Figs. S1, S2, and Tables S6–11: Treatability test (column); Text S3: Basics of isotope analysis; Tables S12-S14: Groundwater field parameters at each monitoring well; Fig. S3: Abundance of dissimilatory sulfate reducing genes in metagenomes assembled. Supplementary data to this article can be found online at doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172298>.

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